

Autoregressive Linear Mixed Effects Models and Dynamic Models for Longitudinal Data Analysis

Ikuko Funatogawa¹, Takashi Funatogawa²

¹ The Institute of Statistical Mathematics, 10-3 Midori-cho, Tachikawa, Tokyo 190-8562, Japan

² Chugai Pharmaceutical Co. Ltd., 1-1 Nihonbashi-Muromachi 2-Chome Chuo-ku, Tokyo 103-8324, Japan

Abstract

Longitudinal data and panel data are both obtained by repeatedly measuring a response variable over time for multiple subjects, and analytical methods for these data have been developed separately across various disciplines. In recent years, however, methodological integration has begun to emerge. In this study, we focus on dynamic models in which the previous response, that is the lagged dependent variable, appears on the right-hand side of the equation. We compare our previously proposed autoregressive linear mixed effects models, developed within the framework of longitudinal data analysis, with dynamic panel models developed in econometrics. The proposed model extends traditional linear mixed effects models by incorporating an autoregressive term, aiming to describe changes in responses over time while allowing for subject specific inference. In contrast, panel data analysis, often used in observational studies, includes unobserved stable individual effects and lagged dependent variables for adjustment. We focus specifically on likelihood-based methods and examine differences in assumptions regarding an initial response, as well as the treatment of random effects and individual effects.

Key Words: Autoregressive, Dynamic, Longitudinal, Panel Data, Fixed Effects, Random Effects

1. Introduction

Analytical approaches to longitudinal or panel data are different in several fields. In biometrics, a linear mixed effects models is a standard model, with various extensions such as nonlinear mixed effects models and generalized linear mixed effects models. The maximum likelihood estimation is often used. These models are useful for handling unbalanced data and for obtaining subject specific inference without requiring the estimation of a large number of parameters. In contrast, in the fields of econometrics and sociology, panel data analysis often emphasizes controlling for unobserved individual effects b_i . These effects play a central role in panel data analysis, as they help adjust for the time-invariant influence of unobserved, stable individual characteristics on the response.

We have proposed autoregressive linear mixed effects models (Funatogawa et al., 2007; Funatogawa and Funatogawa, 2008; Funatogawa and Funatogawa, 2019). These models extend traditional linear mixed effects models—commonly used in longitudinal data analysis—by incorporating an autoregressive term. They belong both to the class of state dependent models and to the class of mixed effects models. While traditional linear mixed effects models are static in nature, the proposed models are dynamic. The current response $Y_{i,t}$ is affected not only by current covariates but also by past time-varying covariates through the previous response $Y_{i,t-1}$. In our previous studies, we investigated models related to autoregressive linear mixed effects models in natural sciences. We emphasized the importance of multiple representations of these models, including the unconditional representation, representation with random asymptotes or equilibrium, nonlinear growth curve representation, differential equation representation, and state space representation, as demonstrated in Funatogawa and Funatogawa (2019).

In this study, we further investigate several dynamic models from the social sciences to explore their relationship with autoregressive linear mixed effects models. We focus in particular on the field of econometrics, where dynamic models are relatively popular and have been

developed in unique ways. Our primary aim in developing autoregressive linear mixed effects models has been to describe changes in responses over time. In contrast, in econometrics and sociology, dynamic panel models that include lagged dependent variables on the right-hand side of the equation are often employed to adjust or control them.

In econometrics, several influential papers on likelihood-based methods for dynamic panel models were published in the early 1980s (Anderson and Hsiao, 1981, 1982; Bhargava and Sargan, 1983). However, these likelihood-based methods did not necessarily become mainstream in econometrics. Around the same time, Laird and Ware (1982) introduced random effects models, that is linear mixed effects models, for longitudinal data analysis in the field of biometrics.

Despite the growing use of dynamic models across disciplines, the theoretical and methodological connections between them have not been thoroughly explored. By examining these relationships, we aim to promote a better interdisciplinary understanding and clarify differences in assumptions, interpretation, and modeling strategies.

In Section 2, we introduce linear mixed effects models, autoregressive linear mixed effects models, and a typical and simple model to investigate the relationships with similar dynamic models in other fields. In Section 3, we introduce dynamic panel models in econometrics along with two alternative assumptions regarding the initial response. Section 4 discusses the relationships among the models and their interpretations. Section 5 concludes with a general discussion.

2. Autoregressive linear mixed effects models and a typical and simple model

2.1 Linear mixed effects models

Let $\mathbf{Y}_i = (Y_{i,0}, Y_{i,1}, \dots, Y_{i,T_i})^T$ be the vector of the continuous response corresponding to the i th ($i = 1, \dots, N$) individual (or subject, unit) measured from 0 to T_i occasions. Linear mixed effects models are expressed by

$$\mathbf{Y}_i = \mathbf{X}_i \boldsymbol{\beta} + \mathbf{Z}_i \mathbf{b}_i + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i, \quad (2.1.1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ is a $p \times 1$ vector of unknown fixed effects parameters, \mathbf{X}_i is a known $(T_i + 1) \times p$ design matrix for fixed effects, \mathbf{b}_i is a $q \times 1$ vector of unknown random effects, \mathbf{Z}_i is a known $(T_i + 1) \times q$ design matrix for random effects, and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i$ is a $(T_i + 1) \times 1$ vector of random errors, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i = (\varepsilon_{i,0}, \varepsilon_{i,1}, \dots, \varepsilon_{i,T_i})^T$. As describe later, the terminology of fixed effects and random effects are sometimes used differently in econometrics. It is assumed that \mathbf{b}_i and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i$ are both independent across subjects and independently follows a multivariate normal distribution $MVN(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{G})$ and $MVN(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{R}_i)$. \mathbf{G} and \mathbf{R}_i are $q \times q$ and $(T_i + 1) \times (T_i + 1)$ positive-definite covariance matrices. Marginally, \mathbf{Y}_i independently follows a multivariate normal distribution with mean $\mathbf{X}_i \boldsymbol{\beta}$ and variance covariance matrix

$$\mathbf{V}_i \equiv \text{Var}(\mathbf{Y}_i) = \text{Var}(\mathbf{Z}_i \mathbf{b}_i + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i) = \mathbf{Z}_i \mathbf{G} \mathbf{Z}_i^T + \mathbf{R}_i. \quad (2.1.2)$$

The marginal log-likelihood function is

$$\log L = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N \{ (T_i + 1) \log(2\pi) + \log |\mathbf{V}_i| + (\mathbf{Y}_i - \mathbf{X}_i \boldsymbol{\beta})^T \mathbf{V}_i^{-1} (\mathbf{Y}_i - \mathbf{X}_i \boldsymbol{\beta}) \}. \quad (2.1.3)$$

The maximum likelihood estimates are obtained from maximizing $\log L$ with respect to unknown parameters in $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ and \mathbf{V}_i . The maximum likelihood estimates of variance covariance components are biased because these do not take account of the decrease of degree of freedoms by the estimation of fixed effects parameters. In this study we consider the case of fixed T and large N . Random effects \mathbf{b}_i is not estimated but predicted as

$$\hat{\mathbf{b}}_i = \hat{\mathbf{G}} \mathbf{Z}_i^T \hat{\mathbf{V}}_i^{-1} (\mathbf{Y}_i - \mathbf{X}_i \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}). \quad (2.1.4)$$

2.2 Autoregressive linear mixed effects models

The autoregressive linear mixed effects models are an extension from linear mixed effects models. Incorporating the term $\rho \mathbf{F}_i \mathbf{Y}_i$ in the right-hand side of the linear mixed effects models (2.1.1), the autoregressive linear mixed effects models are expressed as

$$\mathbf{Y}_i = \rho \mathbf{F}_i \mathbf{Y}_i + \mathbf{X}_i \boldsymbol{\beta} + \mathbf{Z}_i \mathbf{b}_i + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i, \quad (2.2.1)$$

where \mathbf{F}_i is a $(T_i + 1) \times (T_i + 1)$ matrix whose elements just below the diagonal are 1 and the other elements are 0. Then, $\mathbf{F}_i \mathbf{Y}_i = (0, Y_{i,0}, Y_{i,1}, \dots, Y_{i,T_i-1})^T$ is the vector of the previous response and ρ is an unknown scaler parameter. The variance covariance matrix of \mathbf{Y}_i given $\mathbf{F}_i \mathbf{Y}_i$ is

$$\mathbf{V}_i = \text{Var}(\mathbf{Z}_i \mathbf{b}_i + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i) = \mathbf{Z}_i \mathbf{G} \mathbf{Z}_i^T + \mathbf{R}_i.$$

The marginal log-likelihood function is

$$\log L = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N \{ (T_i + 1) \log(2\pi) + \log|\mathbf{V}_i| + (\mathbf{Y}_i - \rho \mathbf{F}_i \mathbf{Y}_i - \mathbf{X}_i \boldsymbol{\beta})^T \mathbf{V}_i^{-1} (\mathbf{Y}_i - \rho \mathbf{F}_i \mathbf{Y}_i - \mathbf{X}_i \boldsymbol{\beta}) \}. \quad (2.2.2)$$

If the design is balanced, that is same $T_i (\equiv T)$ and \mathbf{V}_i for all individual, the marginal log-likelihood function is

$$\log L = -\frac{1}{2} \{ N(T + 1) \log 2\pi + N \log|\mathbf{V}| + \sum_{i=1}^N (\mathbf{Y}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}_i)^T \mathbf{V}_i^{-1} (\mathbf{Y}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}_i) \}, \quad (2.2.3)$$

with $\boldsymbol{\mu}_i = \rho \mathbf{F}_i \mathbf{Y}_i + \mathbf{X}_i \boldsymbol{\beta}$. In the later sections, we use the equation (2.2.3) with different $\boldsymbol{\mu}_i$ and \mathbf{V}_i .

The marginal (unconditional) representation of (2.2.1), that is the equation which does not include \mathbf{Y}_i in the right-hand side, is

$$\mathbf{Y}_i = (\mathbf{I}_i - \rho \mathbf{F}_i)^{-1} (\mathbf{X}_i \boldsymbol{\beta} + \mathbf{Z}_i \mathbf{b}_i + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i). \quad (2.2.4)$$

Because ρ is a nonlinear parameter, the model is a nonlinear mixed effects model with $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ and \mathbf{b}_i being linear. Because all random effects parameters are linear, the model has a closed form of likelihood. The variance covariance matrix of \mathbf{Y}_i is

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_i \equiv \text{Var}(\mathbf{Y}_i) = (\mathbf{I}_i - \rho \mathbf{F}_i)^{-1} \mathbf{V}_i \{ (\mathbf{I}_i - \rho \mathbf{F}_i)^{-1} \}^T = (\mathbf{I}_i - \rho \mathbf{F}_i)^{-1} (\mathbf{Z}_i \mathbf{G} \mathbf{Z}_i^T + \mathbf{R}_i) \{ (\mathbf{I}_i - \rho \mathbf{F}_i)^{-1} \}^T.$$

The marginal log-likelihood function is

$$\log L = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N \{ n_i \log(2\pi) + \log|\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_i| + (\mathbf{Y}_i - (\mathbf{I}_i - \rho \mathbf{F}_i)^{-1} \mathbf{X}_i \boldsymbol{\beta})^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_i^{-1} (\mathbf{Y}_i - (\mathbf{I}_i - \rho \mathbf{F}_i)^{-1} \mathbf{X}_i \boldsymbol{\beta}) \}, \quad (2.2.5)$$

where $\log|\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_i|$ is equal to $\log|\mathbf{V}_i|$. We can obtain the maximum likelihood estimates based on either (2.2.2) or (2.2.5). When some elements of \mathbf{Y}_i are intermittently missing but the corresponding elements of \mathbf{X}_i are known, we can use only (2.2.5) with deleting the missing part of \mathbf{Y}_i and the corresponding parts of $(\mathbf{I}_i - \rho \mathbf{F}_i)^{-1} \mathbf{X}_i$ and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_i$. Random effects are predicted as

$$\hat{\mathbf{b}}_i = \hat{\mathbf{G}} \{ (\mathbf{I}_i - \hat{\rho} \mathbf{F}_i)^{-1} \mathbf{Z}_i \}^T \hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_i^{-1} \{ \mathbf{Y}_i - (\mathbf{I}_i - \hat{\rho} \mathbf{F}_i)^{-1} \mathbf{X}_i \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}} \}. \quad (2.2.6)$$

2.3 A typical and simple model

To compare autoregressive linear mixed effects models with dynamic models in other fields, we consider the following typical and simple model of an autoregressive linear mixed effects model with just two random effects: a random baseline b_{0i} for $t = 0$ and a random individual effect b_i for $t > 0$. The model is

$$Y_{i,0} = \beta_0 + b_{0i} + \varepsilon_{(AR)i,0}, \quad (2.3.1)$$

$$Y_{i,t} = \rho Y_{i,t-1} + X_{i,t} \beta_x + \beta_{\text{int}} + b_i + \varepsilon_{(AR)i,t}. \quad (2.3.2)$$

For simplicity, we consider only one time-varying covariate $X_{i,t}$ with the unknown parameter β_x and intercept β_{int} for $t > 0$. The random effects b_{0i} and b_i are assumed to be correlated. The $\varepsilon_{(AR)i,t}$ is an independent error in (2.3.2), and it becomes an AR(1) error in the marginal (unconditional) representation (2.2.4). If the AR(1) error is stationary, the variance of $\varepsilon_{(AR)i,0}$ is $\sigma_{AR}^2 / (1 - \rho^2)$. Because an independent error structure is often used in econometrics, we focus on an independent error structure. In Section 4.4, we briefly discuss an additional independent error in the marginal (unconditional) representation (2.2.4). The (j, k) element of the typical variance covariance matrix \mathbf{V}_i ($j = 0, 1, \dots, T_i, k = 0, 1, \dots, T_i$) is $V_{00} = \sigma_{b_0}^2 + \sigma_{AR}^2 / (1 - \rho^2)$, $V_{0j} = V_{j0} = \sigma_{b_0 b}$ ($j \neq 0$), $V_{jj} = \sigma_b^2 + \sigma_{AR}^2$ ($j \neq 0$), and $V_{jk} = \sigma_b^2$ ($j \neq 0, k \neq 0$ and $j \neq k$).

For vector representation, each vector and matrix (for $t = 0, 1, 2, 3$) is

$$\mathbf{Y}_i = \begin{pmatrix} Y_{i,0} \\ Y_{i,1} \\ Y_{i,2} \\ Y_{i,3} \end{pmatrix}, \mathbf{F}_i \mathbf{Y}_i = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} Y_{i,0} \\ Y_{i,1} \\ Y_{i,2} \\ Y_{i,3} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ Y_{i,0} \\ Y_{i,1} \\ Y_{i,2} \end{pmatrix}, \mathbf{X}_i = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & X_{i,1} \\ 0 & 1 & X_{i,2} \\ 0 & 1 & X_{i,3} \end{pmatrix}, \boldsymbol{\beta} = \begin{pmatrix} \beta_0 \\ \beta_{\text{int}} \\ \beta_x \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\mathbf{Z}_i = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \mathbf{b}_i = \begin{pmatrix} b_{0i} \\ b_i \end{pmatrix}, \mathbf{G} = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{b_0}^2 & \sigma_{b_0 b} \\ \sigma_{b_0 b} & \sigma_b^2 \end{pmatrix}, \mathbf{R}_i = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{AR}^2 / (1 - \rho^2) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_{AR}^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sigma_{AR}^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \sigma_{AR}^2 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The typical variance covariance matrix \mathbf{V}_i (for $t = 0, 1, 2, 3$) is

$$\mathbf{V}_i = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{b_0}^2 & \sigma_{b_0b} & \sigma_{b_0b} & \sigma_{b_0b} \\ \sigma_{b_0b} & \sigma_b^2 & \sigma_b^2 & \sigma_b^2 \\ \sigma_{b_0b} & \sigma_b^2 & \sigma_b^2 & \sigma_b^2 \\ \sigma_{b_0b} & \sigma_b^2 & \sigma_b^2 & \sigma_b^2 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{AR}^2/(1-\rho^2) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_{AR}^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sigma_{AR}^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \sigma_{AR}^2 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.3.3)$$

The log-likelihood function of this model is the equation (2.2.3) with \mathbf{V}_i (2.3.3) and the following $\boldsymbol{\mu}_i$ (for $t = 0, 1, 2, 3$),

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_i = (\beta_0, \rho Y_{i,0} + X_{i,1}\beta_x + \beta_{\text{int}}, \rho Y_{i,1} + X_{i,2}\beta_x + \beta_{\text{int}}, \rho Y_{i,2} + X_{i,3}\beta_x + \beta_{\text{int}})^T. \quad (2.3.4)$$

The matrix \mathbf{V}_i has four unique elements ($V_{00}, V_{0j} = V_{j0}$ ($j \neq 0$), V_{jj} ($j \neq 0$), and otherwise) and four unknown parameters ($\sigma_{b_0}^2, \sigma_b^2, \sigma_{b_0b}$ and σ_{AR}^2) except ρ which also appears in the equation (2.3.2).

Assuming $\rho \neq 1$, the model can be transformed to

$$Y_{i,t} - Y_{i,t-1} = (1 - \rho)(\mu_{\text{asym } i,t} - Y_{i,t-1}) + \varepsilon_{(AR)i,t},$$

where $\mu_{\text{asym } i,t} = (1 - \rho)^{-1}(X_{i,t}\beta_x + \beta_{\text{int}} + b_i)$. The autoregressive linear mixed model is interpreted as a model of the response change $Y_{i,t} - Y_{i,t-1}$. Assuming $0 < \rho < 1$, $\mu_{\text{asym } i,t}$ can be interpreted as the asymptotes (or equilibrium) for the i th subject at occasion t and $\mu_{\text{asym } i,t} - Y_{i,t-1}$ as the size remaining to the asymptote. Then, the expected change is proportional to the size remaining with a proportional constant $(1 - \rho)$. With $b_{ai} = (1 - \rho)^{-1}b_i$, $\mu_{\text{asym } i,t} = (1 - \rho)^{-1}(X_{i,t}\beta_x + \beta_{\text{int}}) + b_{ai}$, and b_{ai} is a random effect on the asymptote in this model.

3. Dynamic panel models in econometrics

3.1 Dynamic panel model

Anderson and Hsiao (1982) presented log-likelihood functions under various settings with different assumptions on the initial response $Y_{i,0}$ and other model components. Hsiao (2014) also provided detailed explanation. Here, we focused on two of them, the initial response is random and correlated with the individual effect, and the initial state of the unobserved process is independent of the individual effects (Anderson and Hsiao, 1982; Hsiao, 2014).

Consider the following dynamic panel model:

$$Y_{i,t} = \rho Y_{i,t-1} + X_{i,t}\beta_x + \beta_{\text{int}} + b_i + \varepsilon_{(AR)i,t}. \quad (3.1.1)$$

We assume b_i and $\varepsilon_{(AR)i,t}$ follow normal distributions, $b_i \sim N(0, \sigma_b^2)$ and $\varepsilon_{(AR)i,t} \sim N(0, \sigma_{AR}^2)$, respectively. The random effect b_i is independent with $X_{i,t}$ and $\varepsilon_{(AR)i,t}$. For simplicity, we consider only one time-varying exogenous variable $X_{i,t}$ with the unknown parameter β_x and intercept β_{int} . The equation (3.1.1) is same with the equation (2.3.2) and other assumptions are same except the initial response. There are no assumptions on $Y_{i,0}$ yet.

3.2 Initial response being random and correlated with the individual effect

Firstly, we assume the initial response $Y_{i,0}$ is random and follows a normal distribution $N(\beta_0, \sigma_{y_0}^2)$, and it is correlated with the random individual effect b_i with the covariance $\phi\sigma_{y_0}^2$. Under this assumption, Anderson and Hsiao (1982) provided the log-likelihood function as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \log L = & -\frac{NT}{2} \log 2\pi - \frac{N(T-1)}{2} \log \sigma_{AR}^2 - \frac{N}{2} \log [\sigma_{AR}^2 + T(\sigma_b^2 - \phi\sigma_{y_0}^2)] - \\ & \frac{1}{2\sigma_{AR}^2} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{t=1}^T [Y_{i,t} - \rho Y_{i,t-1} - X_{i,t}\beta_x - \beta_{\text{int}} - \phi(Y_{i,0} - \beta_0)]^2 + \\ & \frac{\sigma_b^2 - \phi\sigma_{y_0}^2}{2\sigma_{AR}^2 [\sigma_{AR}^2 + T(\sigma_b^2 - \phi\sigma_{y_0}^2)]} \sum_{i=1}^N \left\{ \sum_{t=1}^T [Y_{i,t} - \rho Y_{i,t-1} - X_{i,t}\beta_x - \beta_{\text{int}} - \phi(Y_{i,0} - \beta_0)] \right\}^2 - \frac{N}{2} \log 2\pi - \frac{N}{2} \log \sigma_{y_0}^2 - \frac{1}{2\sigma_{y_0}^2} \sum_{i=1}^N (Y_{i,0} - \beta_0)^2. \quad (3.2.1) \end{aligned}$$

As shown in (3.2.1), the log-likelihood function is often presented in terms of time components in econometric literature. This log-likelihood is also presented with the initial response distribution separately. Although it may not be obvious at first glance, this log-likelihood function (3.2.1) is expressed using vectors and matrices as the equation (2.2.3). In the log-

likelihood function (2.2.3), in the case of four time points ($t = 0,1,2,3$), $\boldsymbol{\mu}_i$ is same with (2.3.4) and \mathbf{V}_i is

$$\mathbf{V}_i = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{y_0}^2 & \phi\sigma_{y_0}^2 & \phi\sigma_{y_0}^2 & \phi\sigma_{y_0}^2 \\ \phi\sigma_{y_0}^2 & \sigma_b^2 + \sigma_{AR}^2 & \sigma_b^2 & \sigma_b^2 \\ \phi\sigma_{y_0}^2 & \sigma_b^2 & \sigma_b^2 + \sigma_{AR}^2 & \sigma_b^2 \\ \phi\sigma_{y_0}^2 & \sigma_b^2 & \sigma_b^2 & \sigma_b^2 + \sigma_{AR}^2 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3.2.2)$$

This matrix \mathbf{V}_i has four unique elements and four unknown parameters.

3.3 Initial state of unobserved process being independent of the individual effects

Next, in the other setting, Anderson and Hsiao (1982) introduced the unobserved process $\{s_{i,t}\}$ which is independent of the individual effect b_{ai} (i.e. individual effect b_i with $(1-\rho)b_{ai} = b_i$). The model is

$$s_{i,t} = \rho s_{i,t-1} + X_{i,t}\beta_x + \beta_{\text{int}} + \varepsilon_{(AR)i,t}, \quad (3.3.1)$$

$$Y_{i,t} = s_{i,t} + b_{ai}. \quad (3.3.2)$$

These equations imply that $Y_{i,t} = \rho Y_{i,t-1} + X_{i,t}\beta_x + \beta_{\text{int}} + b_i + \varepsilon_{(AR)i,t}$, and it is algebraically identical to (3.1.1).

The initial state $s_{i,0}$ is assumed to be independent of b_{ai} (i.e. independent of b_i) as described above and random with mean being β_0 or β_{0i} and the variance being arbitrary $\sigma_{s_0}^2$ or stationary $\sigma_{AR}^2/(1-\rho^2)$. Then the initial response is $Y_{i,0} = \beta_0 + b_{ai} = \beta_0 + (1-\rho)^{-1}b_i$ or $Y_{i,0} = \beta_{0i} + b_{ai} = \beta_{0i} + (1-\rho)^{-1}b_i$. The parameters β_0 and β_{0i} are fixed effects parameters in the meaning of the linear mixed effects models.

The log-likelihood function is expressed by the equation (2.2.3) with $\boldsymbol{\mu}_i$ and \mathbf{V}_i that meet each assumption. In the case of four time points ($t = 0,1,2,3$), $\boldsymbol{\mu}_i$ with β_0 is (2.3.4), and $\boldsymbol{\mu}_i$ with β_{0i} is

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_i = (\beta_{0i}, \rho Y_{i,0} + X_{i,1}\beta_x + \beta_{\text{int}}, \rho Y_{i,1} + X_{i,2}\beta_x + \beta_{\text{int}}, \rho Y_{i,2} + X_{i,3}\beta_x + \beta_{\text{int}})^T. \quad (3.3.3)$$

And \mathbf{V}_i with $\sigma_{s_0}^2$ is

$$\mathbf{V}_i = \sigma_b^2 \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ (1-\rho)^2 & 1-\rho & 1-\rho & 1-\rho \\ 1/(1-\rho) & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1/(1-\rho) & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1/(1-\rho) & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{s_0}^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_{AR}^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sigma_{AR}^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \sigma_{AR}^2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (3.3.4)$$

and \mathbf{V}_i with $\sigma_{AR}^2/(1-\rho^2)$ is (3.3.4), except that $\sigma_{s_0}^2$ is replaced by $\sigma_{AR}^2/(1-\rho^2)$.

3.4 Prediction of initial response

Bhargava and Sargan (1983) proposed to predict the systematic or exogenous part of the initial response $Y_{i,0}$, based on the observed values of explanatory variables. Although the covariate is only $X_{i,t}$ in the previous subsections for simplicity, we introduce $\mathbf{X}_{i,t}$ and \mathbf{X}_{ci} and replace $X_{i,t}\beta_x + \beta_{\text{int}}$ in the equation (3.1.1) with $\boldsymbol{\beta}_x^T \mathbf{X}_{i,t} + \boldsymbol{\beta}_{cx}^T \mathbf{X}_{ci}$. $\mathbf{X}_{i,t}$ is a known $p_1 \times 1$ vector of time-varying exogenous variables, \mathbf{X}_{ci} is a known $p_2 \times 1$ vector of time-invariant exogenous variables, and $\boldsymbol{\beta}_x$ and $\boldsymbol{\beta}_{cx}$ are $p_1 \times 1$ and $p_2 \times 1$ vectors of unknown parameters, respectively. The initial response $Y_{i,0}$ is assumed to be endogenous and is explained by the following reduced form in a simultaneous equations system:

$$Y_{i,0} = \gamma_{\text{int}} + \sum_{t=0}^T \boldsymbol{\gamma}_{xt}^T \mathbf{X}_{i,t} + \boldsymbol{\gamma}_z^T \mathbf{X}_{ci} + u_{i,0}. \quad (3.4.1)$$

Bhargava and Sargan (1983) denoted that the equation (3.4.1) is chosen merely for convenience since their initial theoretical model implies that $Y_{i,0}$ is determined by

$$Y_{i,0} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \rho^k (\boldsymbol{\beta}_x^T \mathbf{X}_{i,-k} + \boldsymbol{\beta}_{cx}^T \mathbf{X}_{ci}) + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \rho^k (b_i + \varepsilon_{(AR)i,-k}).$$

The variance of $\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \rho^k (b_i + \varepsilon_{(AR)i,-k})$ is $\sigma_b^2/(1-\rho)^2 + \sigma_{AR}^2/(1-\rho^2)$. Adding a prediction error $\sigma_{\varepsilon_0 p}^2$, the variance of $Y_{i,0}$ is

$$V_{00} = \frac{\sigma_b^2}{(1-\rho)^2} + \frac{\sigma^2}{1-\rho^2} + \sigma_{\varepsilon_0 p}^2.$$

Other elements of \mathbf{V}_i is same with (3.3.4). In the case of four time points, \mathbf{V}_i is

$$\mathbf{V}_i = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\sigma_b^2}{(1-\rho)^2} + \frac{\sigma_{AR}^2}{1-\rho^2} + \sigma_{\epsilon_{0p}}^2 & \sigma_b^2/(1-\rho) & \sigma_b^2/(1-\rho) & \sigma_b^2/(1-\rho) \\ \sigma_b^2/(1-\rho) & \sigma_b^2 + \sigma_{AR}^2 & \sigma_b^2 & \sigma_b^2 \\ \sigma_b^2/(1-\rho) & \sigma_b^2 & \sigma_b^2 + \sigma_{AR}^2 & \sigma_b^2 \\ \sigma_b^2/(1-\rho) & \sigma_b^2 & \sigma_b^2 & \sigma_b^2 + \sigma_{AR}^2 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3.4.2)$$

In (3.4.2), V_{00} and V_{0j} ($j \neq 0$) are based on the stationarity assumption. They also considered unconstrained parameters for V_{00} and V_{j0} . They also considered the unconstrained matrix for \mathbf{V}_i .

4 Relationship and interpretation

In the previous sections, we considered several dynamic models with different assumptions on the initial response. The differences across models appear in $E(Y_{i,0})$, V_{00} , and $V_{0j} = V_{j0}$ ($j \neq 0$), and Table 1 summarizes the assumptions in each model.

Table 1. Assumptions on initial response

	Key assumptions	$E(Y_{i,0})$	V_{00}	$V_{0j}(j \neq 0)$	Eq. for \mathbf{V}_i
(1)	Correlated $b_{i,0}, b_i$	β_0	$\sigma_{b_0}^2 + \frac{\sigma_{AR}^2}{1-\rho^2}$	σ_{b_0b}	(2.3.3)
(2)	Correlated $Y_{i,0}, b_i$	β_0	$\sigma_{y_0}^2$	$\phi\sigma_{y_0}^2$	(3.2.2)
(3)	Independent $s_{i,0}, b_i$	β_0 or β_{0i}	$\sigma_b^2/(1-\rho)^2 + \sigma_{s_0}^2$	$\sigma_b^2/(1-\rho)$	(3.3.4)
(4)	Independent $s_{i,0}, b_i$	β_0 or β_{0i}	$\sigma_b^2/(1-\rho)^2 + \frac{\sigma_{AR}^2}{1-\rho^2}$	$\sigma_b^2/(1-\rho)$	
(5)	Independent $s_{i,0}, b_i$ with prediction error	See (3.4.1)	$\frac{\sigma_b^2}{(1-\rho)^2} + \frac{\sigma_{AR}^2}{1-\rho^2} + \sigma_{\epsilon_{0p}}^2$	$\sigma_b^2/(1-\rho)$	(3.4.2)

(1) Autoregressive liner mixed effects model, (2)-(5) Dynamix panel models in econometrics

4.1 Mean structure

For a fixed T and large N , the maximum likelihood is consistent based on (2.2.3) with mean structure (2.3.4) with β_0 , but inconsistent with mean structure (3.3.3) because of the incidental parameter problem caused by β_{0i} . The number of nuisance parameters, β_{0i} , increases with N , hence maximum likelihood gives inconsistent results for inference about parameters of interest such as ρ , β_x , and β_{int} .

For the case of assuming β_{0i} , Bhargava and Sargan (1983) got around the issue of the incidental parameter associated with the initial response, $Y_{i,0}$, by projecting $Y_{i,0}$ on \mathbf{X}_i under the assumption that b_i and \mathbf{X}_i are uncorrelated (Hsiao, 2014).

One solution for the incidental parameter problem β_{0i} is to use a random effect b_{0i} in a mixed effects model. In this model framework, b_{0i} is not estimated but a small number of distribution parameters $\sigma_{b_0}^2$ and σ_{b_0b} are estimated, and we can predict b_{0i} corresponding to (2.3.3) by (2.2.6). As another specification, in Section 4.3, we introduce b_{s0i} , which is independent of $b_{ai} = (1-\rho)^{-1}b_i$.

4.2 Mixed effects models and marginal models

One of useful points of linear mixed effects models is that they provide subject specific interpretation. Before considering complex cases of dynamic models, we show a simpler example in static models. The variance covariance structure induced by a random individual effects b_i , that is random intercept, and the compound symmetry structure (for $t = 1,2,3$) are

$$\mathbf{V}_b = \sigma_b^2 \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{ME}^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_{ME}^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sigma_{ME}^2 \end{pmatrix} \text{ and } \mathbf{V}_{CS} = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma^2 & \sigma & \sigma \\ \sigma & \sigma^2 & \sigma \\ \sigma & \sigma & \sigma^2 \end{pmatrix}.$$

\mathbf{V}_b and \mathbf{V}_{CS} are marginally same structures, but interpretation and constrains are different. In addition to the marginal expectation of the response $E(\mathbf{Y}_i) = \mathbf{X}_i\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}$, we can obtain the subject specific prediction $E(\mathbf{Y}_i|b_i) = \mathbf{X}_i\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}} + \hat{b}_i$ using the equation (2.1.4). In the case of a random

intercept, $E(\mathbf{Y}_i|\mathbf{b}_i)$ is shifted from $E(\mathbf{Y}_i)$ by \mathbf{b}_i at all time points. There is no such interpretation in \mathbf{V}_{CS} . The random intercept allows only a non-negative covariance because the covariance is $\text{Var}(b_i) = \sigma_b^2$, but the compound symmetry allows the negative covariance.

The variance covariance structure (2.3.3) of a typical case of the autoregressive linear mixed effects model is marginally same with the variance structure (3.2.2). For V_{00} and $V_{0j} = V_{j0}$ ($j \neq 0$), both structures have two free parameters, σ_b^2 and σ_{b_0b} in (2.3.3) and $\sigma_{y_0}^2$ and $\phi\sigma_{y_0}^2$ in (3.2.2). The autoregressive linear mixed effects model provides the subject specific interpretation with $E(\mathbf{Y}_i|\mathbf{b}_i) = (\mathbf{I}_i - \rho\mathbf{F}_i)^{-1}(\mathbf{X}_i\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}} + \mathbf{Z}_i\hat{\mathbf{b}}_i)$ where $E(Y_{i,0}|\mathbf{b}_i) = \hat{\beta}_0 + \hat{b}_{0i}$. Instead of $Y_{i,t}$ itself, $\mu_{\text{asym } i,t}$ is shifted from $(1 - \rho)^{-1}(X_{i,t}\beta_x + \beta_{\text{int}})$ by $b_{ai} = (1 - \rho)^{-1}b_i$ at all time points in the autoregressive linear mixed effects model.

In the structure (3.2.2), the variance covariance structure for $Y_{i,t}$ ($t > 0$) is specified by random effects, but V_{00} and V_{0j} are marginally specified. Then, similar to \mathbf{V}_{CS} , the structure (3.2.2) is general and somewhat vague about how $Y_{i,0}$ came about and how variability of $Y_{i,0}$ is constructed.

The constrains for (2.3.3) are $\sigma_{b_0}^2 = V_{00} - \sigma_{AR}^2/(1 - \rho^2) \geq 0$, $\sigma_b^2 = V_{jk} \geq 0$ ($j \neq 0, k \neq 0$ and $j \neq k$), and $\sigma_{b_0b}^2 \leq \sqrt{\sigma_{b_0}^2 \sigma_b^2} = \sqrt{V_{00} - \sigma_{AR}^2/(1 - \rho^2)} \sqrt{V_{0j} - \sigma_{AR}^2}$ ($j \neq 0$). The constrain for (3.2.2) is $|\phi| < 1$.

4.3 Initial state of unobserved process being independent of the individual effect

The assumption that $\{s_{i,t}\}$ is independent of the individual effect b_{ai} induces the restriction $V_{0j} = \sigma_b^2/(1 - \rho)$ in the structures (3.3.4) and (3.4.2). The first matrix corresponding to the random effect in the variance covariance structure (3.3.4) is produced by $\mathbf{Z}_i\mathbf{G}\mathbf{Z}_i^T$ with the following combination of \mathbf{Z}_i and \mathbf{G} (for $t = 0, 1, 2, 3$),

$$\mathbf{Z}_i = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \mathbf{b}_i = \begin{pmatrix} b_{ai} \\ b_i \end{pmatrix}, \mathbf{G} = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_b^2/(1 - \rho)^2 & \sigma_b^2/(1 - \rho) \\ \sigma_b^2/(1 - \rho) & \sigma_b^2 \end{pmatrix},$$

where the correlation of b_{ai} and b_i is 1. The following combination of \mathbf{Z}_i and \mathbf{G} also produces the same $\mathbf{Z}_i\mathbf{G}\mathbf{Z}_i^T$,

$$\mathbf{Z}_i = \begin{pmatrix} 1/(1 - \rho) \\ 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}, \mathbf{b}_i = b_i, \mathbf{G} = \sigma_b^2,$$

where \mathbf{Z}_i includes an unknown parameter ρ . In the framework of linear mixed effects models, \mathbf{Z}_i is a known design matrix.

Both expressions produce the same $\mathbf{Z}_i\mathbf{b}_i$, and the random effects in the unconditional representation (2.2.4) are

$$(\mathbf{I}_i - \rho\mathbf{F}_i)^{-1}\mathbf{Z}_i\mathbf{b}_i = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \rho & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ \rho^2 & \rho & 1 & 0 \\ \rho^3 & \rho^2 & \rho & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} b_{ai} \\ (1 - \rho)b_{ai} \\ (1 - \rho)b_{ai} \\ (1 - \rho)b_{ai} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} b_{ai} \\ b_{ai} \\ b_{ai} \\ b_{ai} \end{pmatrix}.$$

In this case, not only $\mu_{\text{asym } i,t}$ but also $Y_{i,t}$ is shifted by $b_{ai} = (1 - \rho)^{-1}b_i$ at all time points. These are a random intercept in unconditional representation.

The stationary assumption $V_{00} = \sigma_b^2/(1 - \rho)^2 + \sigma_{AR}^2/(1 - \rho^2)$ means $s_{i,0} = \beta_0 + \varepsilon_{(AR)i,0}$ and the variability in $s_{i,0}$ is produced by the stationary $\varepsilon_{(AR)i,0}$. The arbitrary assumption $\sigma_{s_0}^2$ does not specify how the variability in $s_{i,0}$ is produced. As with the equation (2.3.1), if we assume the following model for the state $s_{i,0}$ with an additional random effect $b_{s_0i} \sim N(0, \sigma_{b_{s_0}}^2)$,

$$s_{i,0} = \beta_0 + b_{s_0i} + \varepsilon_{(AR)i,0},$$

the model for the initial response is $Y_{i,0} = \beta_0 + (1 - \rho)^{-1}b_i + b_{s_0i} + \varepsilon_{(AR)i,0}$, and the variance of $Y_{i,0}$ is

$$V_{00} = \sigma_b^2/(1 - \rho)^2 + \sigma_{AR}^2/(1 - \rho^2) + \sigma_{b_{s_0}}^2.$$

The structure of \mathbf{V}_i is same with (3.4.2) except that $\sigma_{b_{s0}}^2$ is the variability of the random effect rather than the prediction error.

Hsiao (2014) denoted the differences in interpretation of how $Y_{i,t}$ is generated in the two expressions. The equation (3.1.1) implies that apart from a common response to $Y_{i,t-1}$ and the exogenous variables, each individual process is also driven by the unobserved characteristics b_i . The equation (3.3.1) implies that, conditional on the exogenous variables, individuals are driven by an identical stochastic process with independent (and different) shocks that are random draws from a common population. The observed value ($Y_{i,t}$) of the latent variable $s_{i,t}$ is shifted by time-invariant $b_{ai} = (1 - \rho)^{-1}b_i$. Anderson and Hsiao (1982) also denoted that the unobservable $s_{i,t}$ carry the effected x and can be called a state. In the equation (3.3.2), inclusion of time-invariant individual effect implies the aggregate effect of unobservable variables (commonly called “residual”) are serially correlated in another way.

4.4 Another error structure with state-space representation

Funatogawa et al. (2007) considered the following error structure with an additional measurement error $\varepsilon_{(ME)i,t}$ which is an independent error in the marginal representation (2.2.4).

$$Y_{i,0} = \beta_0 + b_{0i} + \varepsilon_{(AR)i,0} + \varepsilon_{(ME)i,0},$$

$$Y_{i,t} = \rho Y_{i,t-1} + X_{i,t}\beta_x + \beta_{int} + b_i + \varepsilon_{(AR)i,t} + \varepsilon_{(ME)i,t} - \rho\varepsilon_{(ME)i,t-1}.$$

In the case of four time points ($t = 0,1,2,3$), \mathbf{V}_i is

$$\mathbf{V}_i = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{b_0}^2 & \sigma_{b_0b} & \sigma_{b_0b} & \sigma_{b_0b} \\ \sigma_{b_0b} & \sigma_b^2 & \sigma_b^2 & \sigma_b^2 \\ \sigma_{b_0b} & \sigma_b^2 & \sigma_b^2 & \sigma_b^2 \\ \sigma_{b_0b} & \sigma_b^2 & \sigma_b^2 & \sigma_b^2 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\sigma_{AR}^2}{1-\rho^2} + \sigma_{ME}^2 & -\rho\sigma_{ME}^2 & 0 & 0 \\ -\rho\sigma_{ME}^2 & \sigma_{AR}^2 + (1+\rho^2)\sigma_{ME}^2 & -\rho\sigma_{ME}^2 & 0 \\ 0 & -\rho\sigma_{ME}^2 & \sigma_{AR}^2 + (1+\rho^2)\sigma_{ME}^2 & -\rho\sigma_{ME}^2 \\ 0 & 0 & -\rho\sigma_{ME}^2 & \sigma_{AR}^2 + (1+\rho^2)\sigma_{ME}^2 \end{pmatrix}.$$

This matrix has five unique elements, and has five unknown parameters except ρ which appears in the equation for \mathbf{Y}_i (2.2.1).

For this model, Funatogawa and Funatogawa (2008) proposed state space representation. The state equation is

$$\begin{pmatrix} \mu_{i,t} \\ \mathbf{b}_i \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \rho & \mathbf{Z}_{i,t} \\ \mathbf{0}_{q \times 1} & \mathbf{I}_{q \times q} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mu_{i,t-1} \\ \mathbf{b}_i \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{X}_{i,t}\boldsymbol{\beta} \\ \mathbf{0}_{q \times 1} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{(AR)i,t} \\ \mathbf{0}_{q \times 1} \end{pmatrix},$$

and the observation equation is

$$Y_{i,t} = (1 \quad \mathbf{0}_{1 \times q}) \begin{pmatrix} \mu_{i,t} \\ \mathbf{b}_i \end{pmatrix} + \varepsilon_{(ME)i,t}.$$

In this representation, the state vector $(\mu_{i,t} \quad \mathbf{b}_i^T)^T$ and its element $\mu_{i,t} = \rho\mu_{i,t-1} + \mathbf{X}_{i,t}\boldsymbol{\beta} + \mathbf{Z}_{i,t}\mathbf{b}_i + \varepsilon_{(AR)i,t}$ include random effects \mathbf{b}_i . In the observational equation, the measurement error (or residual) is $\varepsilon_{(ME)i,t}$. On the other hand, in the unobserved process $s_{i,t}$ (3.3.1), the state does not include the random effect, and the random effect is considered to be residual as described in Section 4.3. There are some conceptual differences.

5 Discussion

In this study, we investigated several dynamic models published in econometric literatures to examine their relationship with autoregressive linear mixed effects models. We showed that the marginal variance covariance structure of the autoregressive linear mixed effects model with a random baseline and a random intercept for $t > 0$ is same with that of the dynamic panel model under the assumption that the initial response is random and correlated with the random individual effect. The log-likelihood functions of both models can be expressed in the same manner using vector and matrix notation. Notably, the autoregressive linear mixed effects model provides subject specific interpretation.

Since our main aim of developing the autoregressive linear mixed effect model is to express changes in responses over time from baseline, it is natural to include two or more random effects. In contrast, the dynamic panel models presented here include only one random effect, i.e. the random individual effect. The assumption that the individual effect is the same at all time points, including baseline, is considered an assumption of stationarity. Econometric approaches to panel data analysis are strongly influenced by time series modeling.

Anderson and Hsiao (1982) noted that “The maximum likelihood estimator is complicated and depends on the initial condition. Sometimes we have little information to rely upon in making a correct choice of the initial condition. A simple consistent estimator which is independent of the initial condition will be appealing in its own right, and in addition can be used as the initial value to start the iterative process to obtain the maximum likelihood estimator.” They also emphasized that “An investigator should be very careful in choosing the appropriate initial condition so that the chosen model would correspond to the true situation.” These considerations may help explain the limited use of the method.

It has become evident that in both longitudinal and panel data analyses, terminology is often used differently across disciplines and literatures. For example, in panel data analysis, when unobserved individual or unit effects are correlated with covariates, they are sometimes referred to as “fixed effects,” whereas when they are uncorrelated, they are referred to as “random effects.” This usage differs from that in the traditional linear mixed effects models. In econometrics, the correlation between individual effects and covariates is a central concern.

It is important to understand how different fields have developed distinct methodologies. As these approaches have begun to converge in recent years, further refinement and clarification of both theory and methodology are desirable. While we have examined models proposed in adjacent fields, differences may still persist due not only to historical divergences in the methodological development, but also to variations in theoretical frameworks, research objectives, units of analysis, study designs, and disciplinary conventions regarding statistical assumptions and terminology.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by JSPS by KAKENHI23K11022, 2025-ISMCRP-1007.

References

- Anderson TW, Hsiao C. (1981) Estimation of dynamic models with error components. *Journal of the American Statistical Association* 76:598–606.
- Anderson TW, Hsiao C. (1982) Formulation and estimation of dynamic models using panel data. *Journal of Econometrics* 18:47–82.
- Bhargava A, Sargan JD. (1983) Estimating dynamic random effects models from panel data covering short time periods. *Econometrica* 51:1635–59.
- Funatogawa I et al. (2007) An autoregressive linear mixed effects model for the analysis of longitudinal data which show profiles approaching asymptotes. *Statistics in Medicine* 26:2113–30.
- Funatogawa I, Funatogawa T. (2008) State-space representation of an autoregressive linear mixed effects model for the analysis of longitudinal data. *Proceedings of Joint Statistical Meetings* 3057–62.
- Funatogawa I, Funatogawa T. (2019) *Longitudinal data analysis: autoregressive linear mixed effects models*. Springer.
- Hsiao C. (2014) *Analysis of Panel Data. Third edition*. Cambridge University Press.
- Laird NM, Ware JH. (1982) Random-effects models for longitudinal data. *Biometrics* 38:963–74.